

Enclave Urbanism in Jos: Examining Security, Exclusivity, and Housing Commodification

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Abstract

In rapidly urbanising African cities, gated residential enclaves have expanded as responses to insecurity and infrastructure deficits, offering residents both protection and social distinction. In Nigeria, this trend reflects a dual logic: affluent neighbourhoods function as status enclaves, while middle-income areas adopt gating primarily for crime prevention. In Jos Metropolis, shaped by a history of sectarian violence and recurrent insecurity, the demand for gated housing has intensified, with such developments increasingly perceived as both safe havens and symbols of prestige. This paper examined how insecurity drives gated development in Jos, how class and status contribute to the commodification of these enclaves, and how exclusivity reshapes urban cohesion. Drawing on comparative insights from other African cities and using a qualitative review methodology, the study synthesises comparative case studies alongside a thematic analysis of scholarly literature and policy documents, and finds that while insecurity is a key driver of enclave living, gated environments do not necessarily guarantee safety. Instead, they repackage security and lifestyle into market commodities, reinforcing socio-economic fragmentation. The paper concludes that the growth of gated enclaves in Jos, driven by fear and status aspirations, risks deepening spatial inequality and weakening social integration in an already polarised urban context. The paper recommends implementing inclusive urban security strategies, improving public infrastructure, and developing housing policies that promote social integration over spatial exclusion.

Keywords: Exclusivity, Insecurity, Housing Commodification, Enclave Urbanism, Jos, Gated

INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of gated residential enclaves across rapidly urbanising African cities is increasingly associated with rising insecurity and persistent infrastructure deficits. These developments, typically enclosed by walls or fences and regulated through controlled access, are marketed as spaces of safety, privacy, and exclusivity (Titilayo, 2025; Levin et al., 2026). Although gated communities originated in the

late twentieth-century United States as responses to crime and privacy concerns, they have since diffused widely across the Global South, including cities such as Johannesburg, Nairobi, Lagos and Jos (Low, 2004; Blakely and Snyder, 1997; Bandaiko et al., 2022; Ezeanah and Moga, 2025). Evidence from sub-Saharan Africa consistently identifies fear of crime and the pursuit of elite lifestyles as primary drivers of

this form of residential development (Bandaiko et al., 2022). Typically, these enclaves concentrate in peripheral or high-income areas, often supported by privately provided infrastructure and premium services (Titilayo, 2025).

Enclave urbanism refers to the segregation of cities into relatively homogenous and often gated areas, by class, race, religion, or ethnicity. They may be residential, industrial, commercial or recreational in nature, such as gated communities, ethnic enclaves, informal settlements, high-tech parks, export processing zones, retail malls, tourist destinations, and university towns (Wissink et al., 2012; He and Chang, 2020; Korah et al., 2021). In the context of this study, enclave urbanism is a process of urbanisation that results in the formation of specialised and often fortified urban districts as separate investment, governance, and service delivery nodes that foster socio-spatial inequality and uneven urbanisation.

In Nigeria, these broader dynamics are clearly evident. Major cities, such as Lagos, have experienced significant growth in gated housing, with studies distinguishing between "status enclaves" in affluent neighbourhoods and "security enclaves" in middle-income areas, where gating is primarily motivated by fear of crime. Badiora (2023) observes that gated communities serve as markers of prestige among the elite, while middle-income households adopt perimeter fencing and access control as practical strategies to reduce burglary and theft. Similar patterns are observed in Abuja, Port Harcourt, and Ibadan, where gated estates are increasingly associated with improved perceptions of safety and residential satisfaction (Makinde, 2020). These trends suggest that gated housing in Nigeria is shaped not only by security concerns but also by class positioning and residential aspirations.

Jos Metropolis provides a particularly important context for examining these dynamics. As the capital of Plateau State, Jos has experienced

repeated episodes of sectarian violence, most notably in 2001, 2008, 2010 and 2026, along with more recent incidents that continue to reinforce residents' sense of insecurity (Sanda et al., 2024; Mbachii, 2026). In response, demand for gated housing has increased, particularly among higher-income groups seeking both protection and social distinction. In this setting, gated enclaves function not only as spaces of refuge but also as symbols of prestige and modern urban identity. Thus, housing becomes both a defensive mechanism and a means of social signalling+.

Existing scholarship situates these developments within the broader framework of enclave urbanism, in which housing is increasingly commodified and urban space becomes more fragmented. Bandaiko et al. (2022) argue that gated communities in African cities reflect globalised, market-driven urban processes that deliver security and exclusivity to a limited segment of the population while intensifying inequality and spatial segregation. In Lagos, Badiora (2023) and Ajibola et al., (2011) show that gated suburbs concentrate infrastructure and services within enclosed boundaries, reinforcing urban fragmentation. Comparative evidence from Nairobi similarly highlights stark socio-spatial divisions between high-income enclaves and surrounding informal settlements (Jimmy et al., 2020). These patterns raise important concerns for Jos, where the expansion of gated estates may further undermine social cohesion in an already polarised urban environment.

This paper critically examines gated enclave urbanism in Jos Metropolis by focusing on three interrelated issues: the role of insecurity in driving demand for gated housing, the influence of class and prestige in shaping the commodification of these developments, and the implications of exclusivity for urban cohesion. The analysis situates Jos within broader African and global debates through comparisons with cities such as Lagos, Nairobi, and Johannesburg.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Gated Communities and Enclave Urbanism

Gated residential enclaves are increasingly treated by researchers as a distinctive model of urban development. Generally, a gated community is defined as a residential area enclosed by walls or fences, with controlled entries meant to restrict access to outsiders (Schuermans, 2013; Titilayo, 2025; Iqbal et al., 2024). Such communities usually provide private amenities such as parks, swimming pools, gyms, and recreational spaces for residents' exclusive use. International literature identifies three interlinked motivations for gated housing: security, privilege, and urban governance retreat, particularly under neoliberal urban management systems (Low, 2004; Atkinson and Blandy, 2013). In Jos and similar contexts, these motivations manifest concurrently rather than independently (Levin et al., 2026).

Scholars note that gated estates globally arose partly as rational responses to crime and fear. Landman (2019) and Iqbal et al. (2024) explain that increasing crime rates motivate urban dwellers to physically secure their neighbourhoods. In many countries, gated neighbourhoods are actively marketed as crime prevention strategies. Blakely and Snyder (1997) and Low (2001) observed in the United States that fear is the most prevalent rationale for gated living. Bandaiko et al., (2022) similarly reports that, in Africa, most studies link the emergence of gated communities to rising crime and the search for improved living environments and these empirical surveys support this observation. Makinde (2020) found in Ibadan that gated residents reported above-average perceptions of safety, with security features such as gates, guards, and lighting significantly reducing fear.

However, alongside security needs, gated communities also function as symbols of exclusivity and prestige. Bandaiko et al. (2022) and Yekple et al., (2024) note that globalisation has introduced elite lifestyles into African cities,

influencing residential preferences. In Nigeria's major cities, luxury gated estates are explicitly marketed to affluent households. Badiora (2023) highlights that, in Lagos's elite neighbourhoods, the primary motive for gating is status, as gates indicate distinction and social hierarchy. Housing thus becomes a commodity not only of shelter but also of social positioning. Housing purchases in these enclaves signal class identity and embed socio-economic stratification into the urban landscape.

Security-Driven Housing Demand in Nigeria

In Nigeria, insecurity has long influenced residential choices (Adetokunbo, 2013). Beyond conventional crime, cities such as Jos experience ethno-religious tensions and episodic communal violence. Sanda et al. (2024) document that weak governance, youth unemployment, and religious extremism are among the dominant factors shaping insecurity in Jos. In such conditions, gated housing is increasingly perceived as a protective response. Although systematic data on Jos enclaves remain limited, comparable evidence from other Nigerian cities provides useful insights. In Plateau State, households reportedly increased spending on private security measures following violent episodes (Sanda et al., 2024; Abubakar et al., 2024).

Similar patterns are observed elsewhere. In Lagos, Badiora (2023) reports that many households adopt gates and perimeter fencing due to burglary fears. Makinde (2020) similarly found that residents of gated estates in Ibadan perceived themselves as significantly safer than residents of open neighbourhoods. These findings indicate that gated housing responds not only to objective crime levels but also to subjective perceptions of insecurity. In Jos, the additional dimension of ethno-religious conflict intensifies this perception, making gated communities attractive to middle- and upper-income households seeking refuge from broader social instability.

By contrast, lower-income neighbourhoods in Jos often retain open and permeable residential

layouts. Areas such as Angwan Rukuba, Apata, and Dilimi are characterised by limited physical barriers and higher residential density (Mbachii, 2026). This contrast highlights the class-based nature of gated enclave development. Igwe et al. (2025), studying Awka metropolis, similarly observed that gated communities are predominantly occupied by higher-income, formally employed, and better-educated residents. These spatial patterns produce fragmented urban forms marked by socio-economic clustering.

Commodification of Housing and Prestige

The rise of gated communities reflects the broader commodification of housing in neoliberal urban contexts. Housing increasingly functions as a financial asset, investment vehicle, and status symbol rather than solely as a basic human need. Titilayo (2025) demonstrates that gated enclaves in Lagos are sustained through resident-funded infrastructure systems, effectively privatising services traditionally provided by the state. Residents pay premiums for exclusivity, security, and lifestyle amenities, reinforcing the market-orientated character of enclave urbanism.

Bandauko et al. (2022) argue that globalisation has facilitated the diffusion of market-driven residential models across African cities. In Nigeria, elite gated estates are branded with aspirational identities and lifestyle imagery, often mirroring global urban aesthetics. These developments reshape land values and housing markets, driving up property prices within gated zones and contributing to exclusionary urban growth. Badiora (2023) notes that such processes intensify inequality by concentrating on infrastructure investment within enclaves while surrounding neighbourhoods remain underserved. Social Integration and Urban Cohesion

While gated communities may enhance internal cohesion among residents, the broader social consequences are often negative. Scholars argue that gated enclave urbanism weakens social

integration by restricting movement, reducing public interaction, and fragmenting urban space. Low (2004) describes gated communities as prioritising protection over accessibility, thereby undermining collective urban life. In Lagos, Badiora (2023) warns that the proliferation of gated neighbourhoods fuels exclusion and diminishes shared civic responsibility.

Comparative studies reinforce these concerns. In Nairobi, high-income gated suburbs coexist alongside informal settlements, separated by walls and security barriers that limit interaction (Jimmy et al., 2020). These physical divisions exacerbate socio-spatial inequality and reinforce perceptions of social distance. Similar dynamics have been documented in Johannesburg, where post-apartheid gated developments replicate patterns of segregation under new market-driven logics.

In Jos, where social relations are already strained by ethno-religious divisions, the expansion of gated enclaves' risks deepening mistrust and polarisation. As affluent residents retreat into secured spaces, opportunities for everyday interaction across social groups decline. The literature suggests that such fragmentation may ultimately undermine long-term urban security, as exclusion and inequality contribute to resentment and instability (Bandauko et al., 2022; Badiora, 2023).

In general, literature substantiates three fundamental findings. Initially, the demand for gated housing is significant, regardless of whether it is rooted in crime or conflict. However, gates do not ensure safety and can result in unintended relational costs (Makinde, 2020; Sanda et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2020). Secondly, gated estates contribute to the commodification of housing by combining safety, services, and prestige into premium products that exacerbate class-based spatial sorting (Bandauko et al., 2022; Titilayo, 2025; Igwe et al., 2025). Third, exclusivity has a propensity to exacerbate fragmentation and undermine citywide cohesion, particularly in

cases where social divisions are already politically charged (Jimmy et al., 2020; Bandauko et al., 2022). In Jos Metropolis, these dynamics may be reconciled: insecurity increases the willingness to pay for enclosure, prestige reinforces demand among elites, and the resulting spatial segmentation may undermine the ordinary social integration necessary for long-term stability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adopts a qualitative literature review design to examine the relationship between insecurity, exclusivity, and the commodification of housing through enclave urbanism, with a specific focus on Jos Metropolis. As a review paper, the study does not rely on original field data but synthesises peer-reviewed academic literature to develop a critical and contextual understanding of gated housing development in Nigeria and other comparable urban settings. Qualitative review approaches are appropriate for exploring complex and context-specific urban phenomena, particularly where issues of security, inequality, and governance intersect (Ravensbergen and El-Geneidy, 2023; Wolman et al., 2024). Through this approach, the paper seeks to explain how insecurity, socio-economic stratification, and market forces are reshaping residential patterns and urban relations in Jos Metropolis.

The review is both thematic and comparative, drawing on studies from Jos, other Nigerian cities such as Lagos and Ibadan, and selected African cities including Nairobi and Johannesburg. This comparative orientation enables enclave urbanism in Jos to be situated within broader global South urban dynamics shaped by insecurity, neoliberal housing markets, insecurity and exclusivity. The paper's aim is to provide a deeper understanding of how enclave urbanism in Jos intersects with broader urban processes and contributes to the wider discourse on commodification of housing, issues of security and urban exclusivity in Africa.

Data for the review were sourced exclusively from peer-reviewed academic publications accessed primarily through Google Scholar. The materials reviewed include journal articles, scholarly books, and conference papers addressing themes such as gated communities, urban insecurity, housing commodification, residential segregation, enclave urbanism, and social cohesion. Priority was given to studies published between 2010-2025, focusing on empirically grounded research related to Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa. Widely cited theoretical works that provide conceptual foundations for understanding gated development and urban fragmentation were also included.

A structured literature search strategy was employed using combinations of keywords including "gated communities", "enclave urbanism", "housing security", "urban insecurity", "commodification of housing", "social exclusion", "Nigeria", "Jos", "Lagos", "Nairobi", and "Johannesburg". Boolean operators were used to refine search results, and backward citation tracking was applied to identify additional influential studies from the reference lists of key publications (Figure 1). Only studies that were peer-reviewed, methodologically transparent, and relevant to African or Global South urban contexts were included, while non-academic sources, media reports, and studies limited to high-income countries without transferable insights were excluded.

The selected literature was analysed using thematic content analysis, with studies organised around key analytical themes derived from the research objectives: (1) insecurity and the rise of gated housing, (2) social class and housing commodification, (3) real estate marketing and securitisation, and (4) the implications of enclave urbanism for social integration and cohesion. Rather than aggregating findings statistically, the review adopts an interpretive synthesis that emphasises recurring patterns, conceptual tensions, and explanatory insights across studies (see Table 1). This approach allows the paper to

critically engage with how gated communities are framed both as protective responses to insecurity and as market-driven instruments of exclusion, while remaining attentive to the specific socio-political context of Jos Metropolis.

By synthesising this body of literature, the study provides a comprehensive analysis of the

dynamics of enclave urbanism in Jos and situates it within the broader context of urban development in the Global South. This thematic and interpretive review method facilitates a deeper understanding of how the intersection of insecurity, exclusivity, and housing commodification shapes urban experiences and social relations in Jos.

Figure 1: Thematic coding structure for security, exclusivity and commodification of housing in Jos Metropolis

Source: Authors' Design, 2026

Table 1: Sources of Data

Type of Information	Database Searched	Search Phrases / Terms Used (Examples)	Inclusion Criteria Applied	Number Selected for Review
Empirical studies on insecurity, exclusivity, and enclave urbanism in Jos	Google Scholar	“Gated communities Jos”, “urban insecurity Jos”, “residential segregation Jos”, “commodification of housing Nigeria”, “enclave urbanism Jos”	Peer-reviewed; 2010–2025; empirical focus on Jos; English language; relevance to insecurity, housing, and segregation	48
Comparative Nigerian urban studies	Scopus	“Gated communities Lagos”, “ethno-religious conflict Nigeria”, “housing commodification Lagos”, “social exclusion Nigeria”	Peer-reviewed; comparative relevance; urban housing context in Nigeria and the Global South	24
African comparative urban studies	Web of Science	“Gated communities Africa”, “urban fragmentation sub-Saharan Africa”, “Nairobi gated communities”, “Johannesburg urban fragmentation”	African case relevance; conceptual and empirical contributions; 2010–2025	16
Conceptual and theoretical works on enclave urbanism and social exclusion	Backward Reference Search	Reference lists of Low (2004), Bandauko et al. (2022), Caldeira (2000)	Conceptual depth; theoretical contribution to gated development, urban fragmentation, and socio-spatial segregation	18
Policy and institutional reports for contextual support	Policy Reports / Grey Literature	“Urban insecurity reports Nigeria”, “housing conflict Africa”, “gated communities policy Nigeria”	Institutionally credible; non-analytical pieces excluded; contextual relevance to urban insecurity and housing	8
TOTAL	—	—	—	114 studies included

Source: Authors' work, 2026

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section explores the key factors driving the expansion of gated enclave housing, focusing on three main themes: insecurity, social class, and real estate marketing. First, it examines how insecurity, including crime and communal violence, influences the demand for gated housing. It then delves into how social class and

the commodification of housing contribute to the growth of these enclaves, particularly among wealthier residents seeking status and security. Finally, this section discusses the role of real estate marketing in securitising housing and promoting gated communities as desirable, exclusive, and safe spaces. These factors together highlight the complex dynamics shaping urban residential patterns and the implications for social inequality.

Insecurity and the Expansion of Gated Enclave Housing

Across the reviewed literature, insecurity emerges as a consistent trigger for gated housing demand, but the “insecurity” being responded to is not uniform. In many cities it is framed mainly as everyday crime, while in conflict-affected contexts it extends to communal tensions, uncertainty, and perceived threats that go beyond burglary and theft. Evidence from Nigeria aligns with broader Global South patterns in which fear and risk perception strongly shape residential choice and spatial sorting (Qureshi, 2025; Jones and Kotarska, 2025).

In Nigeria, empirical work shows that the perceived safety premium associated with gating is a powerful motivator, and it is often linked to visible security infrastructure (guards, gates, patrols, lighting, and surveillance). Makinde (2020) and Adeniyi et al., (2024) demonstrate in Ibadan that residents’ perception of safety is significantly associated with gating and related security cues. Studies on security and residential environments also emphasise that insecurity operates as a behavioural driver that interacts with socio-economic status; those who can pay are more likely to purchase “risk reduction” through housing form and location (Levin et al., 2026). The property market responds accordingly: research on gated estates shows security features are frequently priced into rent and value, reinforcing the idea that safety becomes an exchangeable housing attribute (Adeniyi et al., 2024).

For Jos, the security logic is shaped by a distinctive context: the city’s experience of ethno-religious tension and communal violence strengthens demand for residential forms that signal control, predictability, and restricted access (Madueke and Vermeulen, 2018; Nnabuihe, 2020). Recent work on residential neighbourhood security in Jos links insecurity to governance challenges, unemployment

pressures, and social tensions, reinforcing the plausibility of security-driven residential retreat and privatised protection in housing decisions (Onoja, 2015; Sanda et al., 2024). In parallel, security scholarship increasingly emphasises how residents construct insecurity locally (“vernacular security”) and translate it into everyday protective strategies, including residential relocation, enclosure, and reliance on non-state security arrangements and processes that are highly relevant to Plateau State’s broader security environment.

At the same time, international evidence urges caution about assuming gates automatically generate safety. Comparative research finds mixed outcomes: gating may change perceptions, but it can also reduce neighbourhood relations and, through that pathway, undermine the very sense of safety it is assumed to enhance (Zhang et al., 2020). This matters in Jos because the security argument for enclaves can become self-reinforcing: fear increases gating, gating increases separation, and separation can weaken trust and informal social control, which are crucial to everyday security in many Nigerian neighbourhoods (Sanda et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2020).

Social Class, Prestige, and the Commodification of Housing

The literature also shows that gated enclave growth is not only a response to insecurity; it is strongly entangled with class formation, prestige consumption, and housing commodification. In African cities, gated communities are repeatedly discussed as products of market-oriented urban change where housing is packaged as a lifestyle commodity and a social marker, not simply a dwelling (Bandauko et al., 2022). This is consistent with housing inequality scholarship that emphasises how market mechanisms, differentiated access, and spatial sorting produce durable patterns of exclusion through housing (Libertun de Duren, 2012).

Recent Nigerian research demonstrates that gating intersects with socio-economic stratification: higher-income households are more likely to select or prefer secured estates, and their preferences are tied to both security and social positioning (Igwe, et al., 2025; Makinde, 2020). Igwe et al., (2025) highlight how socio-economic demographics relate to security characteristics and residential experiences in urban housing contexts, reinforcing the view that gated living frequently consolidates class homogeneity. Even where residents justify gating as "security", the literature suggests that status and distinction remain embedded in how enclaves are designed, priced, and narrated (Bandauko et al., 2022).

The commodification process becomes more visible when enclave housing is linked to private infrastructure and governance arrangements. Lagos-based enclave research shows how infrastructure provision and management can be reorganised around enclave logics, where residents pay for services and governance becomes semi-private, an arrangement that reinforces the idea of housing as a bundled commodity (Titilayo, 2025). Once security and services are bundled into housing products, affordability becomes a gatekeeping mechanism: the enclave is exclusive not only by walls but also by price and recurring service charges, with inequality effects that extend beyond the estate boundary (Bandauko et al., 2022).

Real Estate Marketing and the Securitization of Housing

A recurring result across the reviewed studies is that real estate marketing actively securitises housing by making safety a central selling proposition and by blending security language with lifestyle and prestige cues. While systematic advertising studies remain limited for Jos specifically, the broader evidence base suggests a common pattern: gated estates are promoted through narratives that convert

insecurity into market demand and frame exclusivity as reasonable, modern, and even responsible (Rahman and Taiwo, 2025).

This is consistent with broader work on private security governance, which argues that urban security increasingly operates through assemblages involving private providers, residential associations, and semi-formal arrangements rather than the state alone (Berg, 2021). Where public policing is perceived as insufficient, marketing aligns with a practical promise: "buy into a package where security is internally managed." In conflict-sensitive cities like Jos, this promise can become especially persuasive because buyers are not just purchasing barriers; they are purchasing a controlled social environment and predictable everyday routines.

Importantly, marketing's securitisation role also has distributive consequences. If safety is increasingly treated as a premium private good, then households outside enclaves remain exposed to the same risks without equivalent protective infrastructure. That creates a spatially uneven security landscape, one that tracks income, location, and access to privatised protection (Berg and Howell, 2020; Otchere, et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this study indicate that the expansion of gated enclave housing in Jos is influenced by a multifaceted interplay of housing commodification, social class, and insecurity. Gated environments are sought by residents as they seek safety and control, particularly in response to insecurity that is exacerbated by communal violence and ethno-religious tensions. In regions with inadequate public security systems, the presence of visible security features, including gates, officers, and surveillance, is considered crucial for guaranteeing personal safety. Nevertheless, gated communities may improve residents'

perceptions of safety, but they do not necessarily result in safer neighbourhoods in general. The social fabric may weaken due to a reduction in social interaction, trust, and informal community security networks that result from the separation of residents.

Additionally, gated enclaves are inextricably linked to socio-economic stratification. The demand for such housing is not solely driven by safety concerns; it is also influenced by social status and distinction. These properties are marketed as exclusive, modern, and prestigious, and richer individuals are more inclined to invest in them. This commodification of housing perpetuates urban inequality, as individuals who reside outside gated estates continue to experience elevated security risks without the same level of protection. The high cost of housing in these enclaves results in the exclusion of lower-income groups, perpetuating social divisions. However, it is a product that combines security, infrastructure, and lifestyle, which appeals to wealthier individuals who prioritise these features over the social implications of their living choices.

The appeal of gated communities is significantly enhanced by real estate marketing.

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- Marketing portrays the gated lifestyle as a rational and essential choice for those seeking safety by portraying security as a desirable commodity and integrating it with lifestyle and status. Nevertheless, this method perpetuates the privatisation of security and results in a spatially unequal distribution of safety, from which only those who can afford it benefit. The gated community offers a controlled social environment in conflict-prone cities such as Jos, but it also exacerbates spatial inequality.
- Ultimately, gated communities may provide a transient sense of security; however, their expansion presents obstacles to urban inclusion and cohesion. The city could be further fragmented, leaving those who cannot afford the security premium behind and reinforcing socio-economic divides if the trend persists without sufficient attention to broader urban security and social integration. To mitigate these effects, urban planners must prioritise inclusive solutions to insecurity and invest in public infrastructure that benefits all residents.

Declaration

Grammarly and quillbot were used for correction of grammatical errors.

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